

MECHANISM OF INNOVATION IN THE FIELD OF LIFELONG EDUCATION

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***Abstract.** The mechanism also includes the emergence of negative feelings, the existence of stereotypes of individual and mass consciousness, innovations that affect the way of life, interests and habits of people can cause painful phenomena in them. This is due to the blocking of vital needs for safety, security, self-affirmation, comfort, etc.*

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The mechanism of innovative activity can be called, all related to best practices, numerous organizational changes in the field of continuous education, achievements of scientific thought and their implementation in practice. The educational process, which occupies a central place in pedagogy, can be considered as innovative, because its purpose is to transfer to students new knowledge for them, the formation of new personality traits. If we had effective methods for studying and evaluating innovation processes, then this would allow us to regulate them, enhance practical benefits and increase focus.

Probably, we will not be able to imagine the mechanism for the emergence of innovative activity and the conditions in which this mechanism can work without comprehending the psychological barriers that inevitably arise when you need to go beyond "one's own system" of coordinates, the usual ways of solving a professional problem, one's own idea of ways of performing activities, to make a transition, at least for a short time, to another platform, another point of view. Such transitions from another culture are very difficult. The new and the unknown always caused people anxiety and mistrust. Consequently, the mechanism also includes the emergence of negative feelings, the existence of stereotypes of individual and mass consciousness, innovations that affect the way of life, interests and habits of people can cause them painful phenomena. This is due to the blocking of vital needs for security, security, self-affirmation, comfort, etc. The innovative process and innovative activity, nevertheless, turns into innovation, then there is at least a well-developed set of methods to stop it. Among them, the most common are the following:

- "the method of concretizing documents" - the main thing is to prevent the breadth of the spread of innovation, the volume of content;

- "piecewise injection method" - the introduction of only one element;

- "the method of eternal experiment" - an artificial delay in the experimental status;

- "Method of reporting implementation" - a distortion of the true implementation;

- "parallel implementation method" - innovation coexists with the old.

Many elements are not replaced by new ones, but continue to operate with them, etc.

The above innovative mechanisms and barriers can also be referred to as barriers to creativity:

1. The tendency to conformism (passive acceptance of the existing order), expressed in the desire to be like other people, dominating over creativity, not to differ from them in their judgments and actions.

2. Phobia to turn out to be a "black sheep" among people, to seem stupid and ridiculous in one's judgments.

3. Phobia to seem too extravagant, even aggressive in its rejection and criticism of other people's opinions. In the conditions of our culture, the following judgment is quite common: to criticize a person means to be ignorant towards him, to show him disrespect.

4. Phobia of retribution from another person whose position we criticize. By criticizing a person, we usually evoke a response from him. The fear of such a reaction often acts as an obstacle to the development of one's own creative thinking.

5. Personal anxiety, self-doubt, negative self-perception ("I-concept"), characterized by low self-esteem of the individual, fear of openly expressing one's ideas.

6. Rigidity ("viscosity") of thinking, which can be considered as a property to use the acquired knowledge "in its final understanding without the possibility of diversity."

The mechanism of innovative activity in behavior is not an adaptation, but the maximum development of one's individuality, self-actualization. The teacher should be imbued with the thought: if someone refuses some of their values and ideals, he violates his moral and intellectual integrity, becomes unhappy, loses his freedom. Freedom implies respect for oneself as a person. In society, there are special techniques that force a person to stop innovative activity. It is useful for the teacher to realize the mechanism of innovative activity in experiences and get rid of psychological barriers, "complexes" that prevent the implementation of innovative activity. The standardization of the behavior and the inner world of the teacher is accompanied by the fact that instructive instructions occupy an increasing place in his activities. The mechanism of innovation activity leads to the fact that the teacher can fit into the pedagogical community, while reducing the level of creativity.

But the development of society, the mechanism of innovative activity, requires the teacher to have innovative behavior, that is, active and systematic creativity in pedagogical activity.

The mechanism of innovative activity in education is what characterizes and organizes the educational process and is a guide for achieving the set learning goals. Consequently, the mechanism of innovative activity in education is a systemic category focused on the didactic application of scientific knowledge, scientific approaches to the analysis and organization of the educational process, taking into account the empirical innovations of teachers and the orientation of this process to achieve high results in the development of students' personality.

Such a mechanism of innovative learning activity consists of the following components:

- learning objectives;
- content of training;
- motivation and means of teaching;
- organization of the educational process;
- student;
- teacher;
- the result of the activity.

The mechanism of innovative learning activity includes two interrelated processes: the organization of the student's activity and the control of this activity.

Considering learning technologies, one cannot help but dwell on modern electronic means, which can be called an element of the innovative learning strategy. Traditional education is characterized by a disciplinary model of education: disciplines are overloaded with redundant information. The strategy of innovative learning assumes such an organization of management of the educational process, in which the personality of the teacher still acts as the leading element, but his position in relation to the student, to himself changes. The nature of management, the impact on students is changing. The position of the student also changes.

One of the priority tasks of education related to the innovation strategy and the mechanism of innovation activity is, first of all, the training of the organizers of the educational process themselves, that is, teachers. Education with the mechanism of innovative activity of teachers has three main goals:

- development of a new style of management;
- development of a new type of analytical thinking, which in turn will be productive;
- formation of new ways of social interactions aimed at the joint implementation of projects and programs.

If a new technology appears today, then there must be a system for evaluating this technology. So, the indicators can be the results of a comparison of technologies by blocks:

- educational and methodical;
- organizational and technological;

In addition, it is desirable to involve expert experts who are able to evaluate the technology from a methodological point of view and from the point of view of software implementation.

Since the comparison of the mechanism of innovation can use indicators measured on a variety of scales (for example, on a scale of "excellent", "good", "satisfactory" or in points), the result of the comparison cannot be expressed in the form of a strict ranking of technologies from best to worst. The choice of technology is determined by the qualifications of the person, personal experience and understanding of the relative importance of individual blocks.

The spread of modern innovative mechanisms in the educational process is hindered by a number of significant factors, such as:

- insufficient equipment of educational institutions with computer and electronic teaching aids;
- as a rule, the lack of access of educational institutions to the Internet and other international information networks;
- lack of scientific and methodological base (electronic manuals, laboratory and control works, tests, etc.) for conducting training sessions;
- insufficient qualification of teachers in the field of modern computer technology, their ignorance of both software and teaching technology;
- and as a result of this, insufficient knowledge of students in the field of handling computers, with material presented in electronic form;
- lack of due attention of heads of educational institutions to this teaching method. These issues can be helped by:
 - retraining of teachers for the development of new innovative teaching technologies;
 - encouraging the development of new methodological multimedia aids by teachers;

- holding on-lain conferences, lectures, seminars and other educational events on the Internet and other information networks;
- development of a network of multimedia classes, laboratories and libraries in educational institutions;
- increasing the number of academic hours of teaching how to work on a computer, on the Internet, with electronic teaching aids;
- conducting scientific and educational work among students on modern information technologies.

Such means of the innovation activity mechanism would allow not only to improve the quality of education, but also to convey knowledge to more people.

A particularly effective way to introduce the mechanism of innovative activity in education is the development and implementation of distance learning through local and global world networks. Unfortunately, such examples in our country are still rare, but the development of this particular type of education promises prospects for residents of areas remote from large cities, villages, disabled people, employed people who seek to receive basic or additional higher or special education. Thus, remotely it is possible to pass exams to universities, receive advice from teachers, test knowledge of subjects, etc.

The mechanism of innovative activity of technology in education allows not only to bring education to the masses, improve its quality and speed up the process of acquiring knowledge, but also make education more accessible in material terms, which is not unimportant at the present time. New computer and information technologies are our future.

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